

THE GUIDE

TO COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH

RENEW Collaborations Team

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Environmental professionals, volunteers, campaigners and researchers are increasingly involving themselves in **collaborative research projects** addressing today's complex, intersecting and increasingly urgent environmental crises. Like the problems they seek to address, these ventures are navigating messy terrain with no easy answers.

[RENEW\(ing\) Biodiversity](#) is a five year interdisciplinary research programme jointly led by the University of Exeter and National Trust. It has been deploying a 'people in nature' approach to reshaping biodiversity renewal through individuals, land managers, business and communities, and includes a dedicated team investigating how to work across professional silos and disciplinary boundaries.

[RENEW's Collaboration Theme](#) has synthesised recent proliferations of academic literature, policy reports and firsthand accounts of this topic with new findings from our [ethnographic 'living lab'](#) and [oral history](#) studies documenting experiences of environmental collaboration. This is the third iteration of our Practice Guide, originally published in 2023 to support RENEW as the project lifted off (following consultation and feedback, V2.0 remains unpublished).

We offer the below 'rules of thumb' for **anyone currently involved with – or planning –** environmental research projects that **bridge across** academic disciplines; environmental topics (biodiversity, climate, energy, pollution...); or sectors (campaigning, policy, volunteering, research, professional practice...). They are designed to work in concert with RENEW's other tools and guidance on more specific aspects of biodiversity renewal.

Our 'rules' – in truth pointers to help you navigate this messy terrain – are oriented towards various roles in research projects but are presented together to foster **transparency, shared understanding and mutual accountability**, essential for good collaborations.

For more information on RENEW, please visit: www.renewbiodiversity.org.uk

<https://renewbiodiversity.org.uk/themes/theme-x3-collaboration-in-practice/>

Our work is ongoing, so if you have any feedback or further suggestions on how to improve this document, please contact the Collaborations team at a.cassidy@exeter.ac.uk or H.Shum@exeter.ac.uk.

FOR EVERYONE

'Everyone' means **all the people working on your project**: researchers, managers, administrators, professionals, campaigners, teachers, learners, and volunteers.

Working across boundaries requires ongoing collective efforts that will change over time.

Resist the rhetoric

Idealised jargon about collaboration, inter/trans/multi-disciplinary, co-production and partnership appears throughout funding guidance, policy, campaigning, and academic writing. Collaborative research always involves negotiating across un-shared expectations and ways of working. **This is normal.**

Do understand **there is no one-size-fits-all model** for collaboration: you're engaging with messy problems and complex situations. Things will go wrong: the knack is working together to navigate the bumps.

Don't put interdisciplinarity on a pedestal. It's common to feel that you aren't 'measuring up' to these ideals: while it's good to be self-critical, don't let this anxiety get in your way.

Collaboration involves learning through everyday working

Do recognise you are deliberately bringing together people with differing perspectives. When you gather, be neighbourly and open-minded (but do say what you think). Expect frictions, sometimes choppy waters, and many surprises: they will help you think differently!

Don't expect collaboration to happen spontaneously: it takes active effort from everyone. Keep talking and decide together how you will do this work, including who does what, when and where.

Do get stuck in! **Show up and get involved** – in formal and informal project activities.

Be curious

Because everyone is coming at the project from different angles (sector/discipline, training, experiences, values...), take time to try and understand each other.

Do avoid jargon and use plain English. Remind each other that it's OK to ask naive or obvious questions.

Don't assume that you know best: stay open to uncertainties and making mistakes.

Breathing space

Interdisciplinary and partnership-based projects can be riskier and more unpredictable than traditional research: navigating differences will take more time and patience than usual.

Do create resilience by building good, respectful relationships where you can **learn from and trust each other**, making it easier to 'disagree well'. This includes taking time away from collaborative and social spaces to focus!

Go places

21st century environmental 'knowledge work' (research, education, communication, campaigning) happens across a layered mix of physical, institutional, natural and virtual spaces, including people's homes.

Do 'host' and 'guest' project activities across organisations, particularly in the early stages.

Do get outside. Environmental research is often enabled by being 'in the field' and using all our bodily senses. Going out into nature creates unique collaborative research opportunities, but also sparks joy, curiosity – and reminds everyone why this work REALLY matters.

Have fun!

Hanging out, having fun, being creative and caring for each other fosters critical support structures for environmental collaboration. They are **not 'nice to haves' but essential** for collaborative research.

Do foster shared passions that can bring people together and draw on the expertise, skills and interests of the project team (artistic practice, crafts, nature walks, book clubs, sports/games...)

Do create convivial informal spaces fostering spontaneous, sociable interaction.

Do share food: eating and drinking together is also fun and can help people relax.

RENEW members eating, drinking, talking and handwaving together

FOR PROJECT LEADS AND ORGANISATIONS

If you lead or manage a research team, funded project or organisation engaging in collaborative research, pay particular attention to the following pointers:

Do What I Do

Do lead by example – all the good practices outlined here are more likely to be adopted if **you model them**.

Create effective spaces for exchange (virtually and in-person)

Do gather your team regularly, through formal and informal activities. Take steps to support dialogue that can surface everyone's values, motivations, perspectives, and expectations.

Don't pretend hierarchies aren't there (career stages, academic/non-academic, gender, ethnicity, class, sexuality, education, health, precarity): when appropriate, take steps to flatten them. Consult with those impacted on *how* to go about this and draw on existing guidance from organisations involved in the project.

Do organise and chair/host inclusively: welcome newcomers and encourage everyone to ask questions and share their perspectives. Keep inviting input from quieter and less senior colleagues (via direct/verbal and indirect/text-based channels, supporting access needs).

Don't expect everyone to have facilitation skills: get yourself and others trained while learning from colleagues with this expertise. In-person and online modes of working need tailored forms of support to foster active dialogue.

Do acknowledge the social, emotional and organisational knowhow, time and effort that makes effective inclusive working possible. Verbalise, resource and practice this support.

Project planning

Do pay for and thank external collaborators for their time, particularly those who are freelancers and from small organisations.

Do consider formally allocating **dedicated time** for team members to put in the extra work needed to enable communication and ongoing interactions across the project. Include budget to support gatherings, including for food and drink.

Do think carefully about project design, creating structured and sensibly timed opportunities for iterative change and for findings from different parts of the project to feed into each other, including formal and informal activities.

Don't delegate the work of organising and facilitating the project to particular groups or individuals: ensure everyone takes some responsibility for this, including yourself.

Navigate organisational differences

Organisational infrastructures will differ: bear in mind these differences are going to be material, technological, bureaucratic and social.

People across the project will be working within different organisational infrastructures. **Do** think carefully about – and plan for – **how** you will navigate across varying working practices. Remember to celebrate the wins!

Timelines, professional expectations and motivations will vary immensely. Differences will continue to crop up throughout the course of the project. **Do** expect to keep negotiating.

Do ensure you have inclusive governance mechanisms (for project planning and ongoing decision-making) to manage day-to-day working and points of friction **as they arise**.

Collaborative research needs structures that can scaffold from above bottom-up, unconventional working

FOR FUNDERS, ASSESSORS AND EVALUATORS

While many of the above recommendations are good practice for research in general, interdisciplinary and partnership-based projects deliberately reach beyond traditional, disciplinary based research infrastructures, can be more unpredictable, and therefore require additional scaffolding.

Do ensure interdisciplinary projects and proposals are assessed by panels drawing on an appropriate range of professional and experiential perspectives. **Don't** assess using a small subset of disciplinary experts.

Do ensure that research funding, assessment and evaluation structures explicitly consider whether **research processes** (including the time and work that will be involved), are realistically designed, costed and implemented throughout the project.

SUMMARY

RENEW's Collaborations Theme has synthesised recent proliferations of academic literature, policy reports and firsthand accounts of environmental collaboration with new research findings to create *The Guide to Collaborative Environmental Research*. We offer 'rules of thumb' for anyone currently involved with – or planning – projects that bridge across academic disciplines, environmental topics or professional sectors. Our 'rules' are oriented towards various roles in research projects but are presented together to foster transparency, shared understanding and mutual accountability, all essentials for good collaboration.

CREDITS

The Collaborations Theme would like to thank the following people for their input:

- Emma Zimmerman, Vanessa Gordon and the RENEW Secretariat team
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- RENEW's Partner Forum, project colleagues and our research participants

Image Credits

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p4: *RENEW colleagues eating, drinking, talking and handwaving together* (credit: Angela Cassidy)

p6: *The Tyne Bridge Arch nears completion* (credit: Tyne and Wear Archives & Museums)

RENEWING Biodiversity through a people-in-nature-approach

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unlock

disruptive

reciprocity

unexpected

ideas changed together

no clear 'lead'

only each other

Found poem from a UKRI funding call
by Rebecca Edgerley

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